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FEATURES OF W. SHAKESPEARE'S WORKS MORPHOLOGICAL PECULIARITIES

ANNOTATION

This article provides information on Shakespeare's morphology. His poems are morphologically analyzed and sources related to poetry are presented. Hence, some grammatical problems are studied. In addition, in this article Shakespeare's works are analyzed.

Key words: modern English, English Reformation, Grammatical category, Germanic languages, Roman or Egyptian, Theory, Sacramental rites, Use of grammar.

V. SHEKSPIR ASARLARINING XUSUSIYATLARI MORFOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLAR

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola Shekspirning morfologiyasi haqida ma'lumot beradi. Uning she'rlari morfologik tahlil qilinib, she'riyatga oid manbalar keltiriladi. Demak, ba'zi grammatik muammolar o'rganiladi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqolada Shekspirning asarlari tahlil qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: zamonaviy ingliz, ingliz reformatsiyasi, grammatik kategoriya, german tillari, rim yoki misrlik, nazariya, muqaddas marosimlar, grammatikadan foydalanish.

ОСОБЕННОСТИ МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЙ У. ШЕКСПИРА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье представлен обзор морфологии Шекспира. Проведен морфологический анализ его стихов и приведены источники, связанные с поэзией. Итак, будут изучены некоторые грамматические проблемы. Кроме того, в данной статье анализируются произведения Шекспира.

Ключевые слова: современный английский язык, английская Реформация, грамматическая категория, германские языки, римский или египетский языки, теория, sacramentalные обряды, использование грамматики.

Shakespeare lived at a time when England was undergoing the revolution in ritual theory and practice we know as the English Reformation. With it came an unprecedented transformation in the language of religious life. Whereas priests had once acted as mediators between God and men through sacramental rites, Reformed theology declared the priesthood of all believers. What ensued was not the tidy replacement of one doctrine by another but a long and messy conversation about the conventions of religious life and practice.

In the England of Shakespeare's time, English was a lot more flexible as a language. In addition, Shakespeare was writing as a dramatic poet and playwright, not as a scholar or historian.

Combine the flux of early modern English with Shakespeare's artistic license (and don't forget to throw in a lot of words that have either shifted meaning or disappeared from the lexicon entirely), and there are some subtle difficulties in interpreting Shakespeare's meaning some 400 years after the fact. As with most popular playwrights of any era, Shakespeare uses language with facility and power, but with a colloquial freedom as well.

In English, one word can be as a noun, an adjective or a verb. And Shakespeare's period marks out greatly. It was a time, when there were new grammatical functions for many words. And William Shakespeare stood on the first stage among his contemporaries. In his works, a word can be turned to another grammatical category.

Shakespeare's innovative use of grammar, however, set him apart from his contemporaries. Shakespeare completely reinvented grammar, breaking away from the conformity of traditional rules. We have to highlight a passage from Hamlet, where Shakespeare plays with the normal rules of English that demand a sentence is structured with the order; subject, verb, object. In the scene the queen says to her son: "Hamlet, thou hast thy father much offended." Nowadays, we would expect, 'Thou has much offended thy father Hamlet'."

Shakespeare used a great deal of SOV (Subject-object-verb) inversion, which renders the sentence as "John the ball caught." This order is commonly found in Germanic languages (more so in subordinate clauses), from which English derives much of its syntactical foundation. Shakespeare also throws in many examples of OSV construction ("The ball John caught."). Shakespeare seems to use this colloquially in many places as a transitory device, bridging two sentences, to provide continuity. Shakespeare (and many other writers) may also have used this as a device to shift end emphasis to the verb of a clause. Also, another prevalent usage of inversion was the VS order shift ("caught John" instead of "John caught"), which seems primarily a stylistic choice that further belies the Germanic root of modern English.

In Shakespeare's noun-to-verb conversions "what are thought of as stable objects are wrenched from their passivity to acquire new vigour as actions," observing further that "metaphor harmonizes well with the flexibility of conversion." This union of metaphor and grammatical conversion is evident throughout Antony and Cleopatra, where shifts from noun to verb simultaneously affirm the fertility of metaphor and displace action from the material to the more fluid metaphorical realm. Whether the characters be Roman or Egyptian, their language persistently coins' new words by incubating the solidity of nouns and adjectives into the dynamic liquidity of verbs. Thus, "joint" becomes a verb at 1.2.91, "safe" at 1.3.55, "dumb" at 1.5.50, "spaniel" at 4.7.21, and "boy" at 5.2.220, while "candy" melts itself into "discandy" at 3.13.166 and 4.12.22.

These conversions garner tremendous dramatic advantages. For instance, Terttu Nevalainen notes that by turning dumb from an adjective into a verb, instead of using the already-available verb "silence," Shakespeare gains both the solidity of an Anglo-Saxon root word (instead of the more abstract, Latinate "silence") and an association with the inarticulacy of beasts - beasts were and are commonly described as "dumb" rather than "mute." Such advantages supplement what is always present in Shakespeare's functional conversion of nouns and adjectives into verbs, the "dramatic energy and economy of expression".

Adjectives are freely used by Shakespeare as adverbs:

“I do know, when the blood burns, how prodigal the soul lends the tongue vows.” (Polonius to Ophelia in Hamlet I:3);

“And you, my sinews, grow not instant old.” (Hamlet I:5);

“Which the false man does easy” (Macbeth II: 3).

We find the two forms of the adverb side by side in:

“She was new lodged and newly deified.” (A Lover’s Complaint. 84).

The position of the article shows that mere is an adverb in:

“Heaven and our Lady gracious has it pleas’d.” (First Part of King Henry the Sixth);

“Ay, surely, mere the truth.” (All’s Well That Ends Well III:5).

Such transpositions as “our lady gracious”, (adj.) where “gracious” is a mere epithet, are not common in Shakespeare. For example: “My lady sweet, arise,” (Cymbeline II:3).

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